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1 МАХСУС СОН

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СПЕЦИАЛЬНЫЙ НОМЕР 1

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RESTORATION OF THE CARIOUS CAVITY IN THE CERVICAL REGION IN CHRONIC DIFFUSE PERIODONTITIS

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ABSTRACT

For filling defects noticeable with a smile, when it is also dictated by the high aesthetic requirements of the patient, his young age, the nature of the profession, you should choose a material with good aesthetic characteristics, that is, composite plastics, however, it is always necessary to maximize compliance with the strict rules of regular individual oral hygiene and completeness of periodontal treatment. The most optimal option is when the restoration of aesthetic defects is carried out at the end of periodontal treatment or at least its stage, when the symptom of bleeding gums is eliminated or significantly reduced. During the active course of the carious process, in adolescents and elderly people who neglect the rules of hygienic oral care, it is more expedient to use glass ionomer cements that provide fluoridation of tooth tissues after filling and having acceptable aesthetic characteristics in the next 2 years.

Keywords: Composite materials, periodont, carious cavity.

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ВОССТАНОВЛЕНИЕ КАРИОЗНОЙ ПОЛОСТИ В ОБЛАСТИ ШЕЙКИ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКОМ ДИФФУЗНОМ ПАРОДОНТИТЕ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Для пломбирования дефектов, заметных при улыбке, когда это также диктуется высокими эстетическими требованиями пациента, его молодым возрастом, характером

профессии, следует выбирать материал с хорошими эстетическими характеристиками, то есть композиционные пластмассы. Однако при этом всегда необходимо максимально добиваться соблюдения больным жестких правил регулярной индивидуальной гигиены полости рта и законченности пародонтологического лечения. Наиболее оптимальным является вариант, когда реставрация эстетических дефектов проводится по окончании пародонтологического лечения или хотя бы его этапа, когда симптом кровоточивости десны устранен или существенно уменьшен. При активном течении кариозного процесса, у подростков и пожилых людей, пренебрегающих правилами гигиенического ухода за полостью рта, целесообразнее использовать стеклоиономерные цементы, обеспечивающие фторирование тканей зуба после пломбирования и обладающие приемлемыми эстетическими характеристиками в ближайшие 2 года.

Ключевые слова: композитные материалы, периодонт, кариозный полость.

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КАРИОЗ БЎШЛИҚНИ ТИКЛАШ СУРУНКАЛИ ДИФФУЗ ПЕРИОДОНТИТДА

АННОТАЦИЯ

Табассум билан сезиларли нуқсонларни тўлдириш учун, у беморнинг юқори эстетик талаблари, унинг ёшлиги, касбининг табиати билан белгиланадиган бўлса, сиз яхши эстетик хусусиятларга эга материални, яъни композит пластмассаларни танлашингиз керак, аммо ҳар доим қатъий эстетик талабларга максимал даражада риоя қилиш керак мунтазам индивидуал оғиз гигиенаси ва пародонт даволанишнинг тўлиқлиги қоидалари. Энг мақбул вариант-эстетик нуқсонларни тиклаш пародонтал даволаниш охирида ёки ҳеч бўлмаганда унинг босқичида, тиш гўштининг қон кетиш аломати кариес жараёнининг фаол жараёнида йўқ қилинганда ёки сезиларли даражада камайганда, ўсмирлар ва қарияларда амалга оширилганда. гигиеник оғиз парвариши қоидаларини еътиборсиз қолдирадиган, кейинги 2 йил ичида тўлдирилгандан ва мақбул эстетик хусусиятларга эга бўлгандан кейин тиш тўқималарини фторланишини таъминлайдиган shisha иономер цементларидан фойдаланиш мақсадга мувофиқдир.

Калит сўзлар: композит материаллари, периодонт, кариоз бушлик.

Introduction. Periodontal diseases are today not only a general medical, but also a social problem. They are characterized by a significant prevalence, lead to early tooth loss and have an unpleasant effect on the body as a whole due to the presence of chronic foci of infection.

At the same time, periodontal pathology is simultaneously accompanied by damage to the supporting structures of the tooth - periodontal and bone tissue of the alveoli, gums together with the periosteum, which inevitably leads to damage to the hard tissues of the tooth. Many of these defects are localized in the cervical region of the front teeth (Black class V) and directly affect the aesthetics of the smile. Defects in the neck and root of the tooth can be caused by a carious process, resorption of hard tissues, erosion, wedge-shaped defect or abfraction. During the treatment of such teeth, in order to ensure a good marginal fit of the restoration, it is necessary to isolate the cavity from the gum, prevent bleeding of the latter and leakage of gingival fluid.

Even 20 years ago, aesthetics was not one of the main tasks of stomatology, but now it appears as one of the important goals of dental treatment. Patients strive to receive high-quality treatment in all respects, realizing that a beautiful smile is an indicator of well-being and social stability. But such a smile is impossible without healthy teeth or teeth that have received the appearance of healthy,

thanks to the efforts of the dentist. Therefore, in the motivation of the patient's arrival at the dentist's appointment, it is often not so much treatment that comes first, as the restoration of the appearance of teeth.

Defects of the hard tissues of the tooth in the area of its neck At present, there is an increase in the prevalence of non-carious lesions of the hard tissues of the teeth and, in particular, wedge-shaped defects. Pronounced stages of such defects are more common in middle-aged and elderly people, but initial manifestations are also observed in young people. The development of wedge-shaped defects gradually leads to a significant loss of hard tissues, the appearance of hypersensitivity of enamel and dentin, dystrophic changes in the pulp. Since this pathology is mainly localized on the vestibular surfaces of premolars, canines and incisors, patients also complain of aesthetic disorders. In the clinic, there is often a combination of wedge-shaped defects with other pathology of hard tissues, in particular. TOM and carious There is still no consensus on the etiology and pathogenesis of wedge-shaped defects. According to Yu.A. Fedorov and V.A. Drozhzhina (1997), the development of such defects is most often associated with the general state of the body, in particular, with disorders of the thyroid gland. The interrelation of the occurrence of wedge-shaped defects with the pathology of the gastrointestinal tract, diseases of the central nervous system was noted. The influence of periodontal diseases on their occurrence and progression is well known. The data on the influence of local factors (the use of excessively abrasive hygiene products and violations of dental cleaning techniques) on the development and progression of wedge-shaped defects are presented. In recent years, many researchers have linked the occurrence of cervical lesions and, in particular, wedge-shaped defects, with the pathology of occlusion. It was found that a small vestibule of the oral cavity, anomalies of attachment of the frenulum of the lower lip, malocclusion anomalies lead to traumatic occlusion. At the same time, functional overload of individual groups of teeth or one of the walls of the tooth socket causes excessive tension in the cortical tissues, contributing to the occurrence of gum recession and dystrophic changes in the cervical areas of the teeth. During the general examination of patients with erosions and wedge-shaped defects of the cervical zone of the teeth, various accompanying pathologies were found: dysfunction and enlargement of the thyroid gland; violation of the function of the genital glands; diseases of the gastrointestinal tract. In the occurrence of pathology of the hard tissues of the teeth, the leading role is assigned to the state of mineral metabolism. Violation of it in the body leads to a decrease in the mineralization of enamel and dentin. When studying the ultrastructure of the surface of erosions and wedge-shaped defects, a decrease in the mineralization of enamel and dentin in the active stage of erosion was found, which was clinically expressed by hyperesthesia of hard tissues. One of the main damages of the hard tissues of the tooth in the area of its neck, which occur after the destruction of the dentoalveolar junction and atrophy of the gum, is caries of cement (or caries of the root). Root caries can become the dominant lesion of the hard tissues of the tooth in elderly and senile people within the next decades. the factors confirming this proposition are the demographic shift characterized by an increase in life expectancy, the preservation of natural teeth until old age as a result of improved dental care, the lack of effective methods of preventing gum recession caused by periodontal diseases. As a rule, root caries occurs in elderly people who have periodontal diseases, which causes the exposure of the root surface. According to various authors, the prevalence of root caries ranges from 15 to 90%. A significant spread of data depends on which population group the study was conducted in: military personnel, people being treated in hospital, living in nursing homes, people taking drugs and isolated populations living in primitive communities. It is known that in Finland the incidence rates are much lower than in North America, which has no explanation yet. Perhaps this is due to the cultural background. Patients with root caries have a more pronounced gingival inflammatory reaction, gingival pocket depth and gingival margin atrophy compared to those who do not have root caries. In an epidemiological study by D. Galan (1993), it was revealed that the age- and gender-adjusted total root caries index (IQC-RCI) was 11.4%, indicating that root caries was detected in approximately one of nine surfaces with gum recession. Although the levels of IQ for men and women were similar, similar indicators by sex for every 10 years of life from 30 to 60 years increased according to the scheme: 1,10-> 4,7%->> 13,0%->> 22,0%. According to M.M. Vehkalahti (1987), the prevalence of root caries varies between

20 and 40%. According to the results of a study by different authors, root caries is more common in men than in women. There is evidence that patients with dental root caries older than 55 years on average have 2.5 teeth more than their peers with crown caries. A study conducted among people aged 60 years and older living in Adelaide and Mont Gambier revealed a wide spread of caries - 49%.

Material and methods of research.

Laboratory and clinical studies were conducted to solve the tasks. Laboratory tests were carried out in the laboratory of JSC "StomaDent". In this paper, we evaluated the effectiveness of aesthetic dental restoration using the five materials listed below.

Composite materials: "UniRest" (CJSC "StomaDent") "Charisma" ("Heraeus Kulzer") and nanocomposite "Filtek Supreme" ("3M Espe"). Glass-polyalkenate (glass ionomer) cements: "Dentis Art" and "ChemFil Superior" (CJSC "StomaDent")

The laboratory tests consisted of two series. The first series was carried out on samples of materials in order to assess their color stability in the presence of blood, the second series of studies was carried out on removed teeth in order to comparatively assess the edge fit of fillings from the listed materials using a dye

The laboratory assessment of the color stability of materials was carried out using the spectrophotometric method according to the "CIELAB" system. This is a generally accepted coordinate system for the instrumental determination of the color of objects, which allows numerically assessing the degree of color difference of colored samples "CIELAB" reflects on the horizontal plane the change in color characteristics-ristik a on a vertical plane — change in the degree of whiteness The study was carried out in accordance with GOST R 51202-98 p 62 "Materials dental polymer restorative Technical requirements Test methods". Possible changes in the color characteristics of materials at the stage of initial hardening under the influence of blood were studied, samples of materials in the form of disks with a diameter of 20 mm and a thickness of 2 mm were made for testing.

These samples were cured by the light of an Optilux photopolymerization lamp (Kegg) with a luminous flux density of 600 mv/mm² by sectors (4 sectors) in 2 modes, Control samples were illuminated for 20 seconds, experimental ones: No. 1 — for 10 seconds, No. 2 - for 20 seconds on both sides

Samples of glass ionomer cements were placed in a chamber with 100% humidity until the end of the curing time, after which their color characteristics were determined, control samples were not exposed to blood, and experimental samples were placed in blood for 3 minutes immediately after manufacture and determination of color characteristics, then washed with running water and the color characteristics of all samples were determined again after determination of color characteristics. the samples were immersed in individual containers with distilled water and placed in a thermostat with a temperature of +37 ° C, where they were for the entire period of the experiment, the color characteristics of the materials were determined immediately after manufacture, after exposure to blood, after 1 and 7 days, after 1, 2 and 3 months.

Measurements of color characteristics were carried out in a spectrophotometer "Color-eve 3000" with software and mathematical software ("Macbeth", USA). The measurement results were recorded in the form of characteristics a, b and L. Quantitative indicators of color change were calculated as the distance separating two color points in the "CIELAB" space.

The examination of patients was carried out according to a single scheme using individual cards, according to its results, an individual treatment plan was drawn up, each patient was introduced to it and received his voluntary written informed consent, both for treatment and for further monitoring of his dental health for at least 3 years

Each patient underwent correction of individual hygiene and professional oral hygiene, which included removal of supra- and subgingival dental deposits, followed by polishing of the surfaces of crowns, necks and exposed areas of the roots of teeth.

Preparation of cavities for restoration in the enamel area was carried out using a turbine tip, and in the dentin area-using a water-cooled micromotor. After drying, the technique of total etching of hard tissues was used.

Conclusions.

Within 3 months after the manufacture of dental restorations from composite materials "UniRest", "Charisma" and "Filtek Supreme", their lightening (in terms of whiteness) is observed by an average of 1% and yellowing by 22.5%. After a 3-minute exposure of blood, the indicators of yellowness and redness of restorations significantly increase in comparison with the control. Restorations made of glass ionomer cements "Dentis Art" and "ChemFil Superior" darken (in terms of whiteness) by an average of 5% in the same period, regardless of the presence of blood. Their yellowness decreases by 18.1%. Contact with blood additionally reduces the yellowness index of "ChemFil Superior" by 17%, and "Dentis Art" — by 3.0%.

Composite restorations made of "Unirest" material have the minimum marginal permeability in the cervical zone of the teeth, and the greatest — from "Filtek Supreme". According to this indicator, glass-ionomer cements are significantly inferior to composites. During 3-year clinical observation of patients with restorations in the cervical zone of teeth and inflammatory periodontal diseases, it was found that composite materials are more color-stable and mechanically stable in comparison with glass ionomer cements. When they are used, a violation of the marginal fit is less often detected. For the aesthetic restoration of defects in hard tooth tissues in periodontal patients, it is advisable to use modern UniRest composite materials, "Charisma" and "Filtek Supreme", taking into account possible color changes in the conditions of bleeding gums. The domestic material "UniRest" is not inferior in its basic properties to its foreign counterparts.

The best results of aesthetic restoration of teeth in patients with inflammatory periodontal diseases can be achieved, guided by the developed algorithm of individual work with the patient, provided that comprehensive periodontal treatment is carried out, including control of individual oral hygiene and correction of motivation for treatment.

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